

1 **Molecular dynamics analysis of N-acetyl-D-glucosamine against specific SARS-CoV-2's**
2 **pathogenicity factors**

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13

14 **Abstract**

15 *Background:* The causative agent of virus disease outbreak in the world identified as SARS-
16 CoV-2 leads to a severe respiratory illness similar to that of SARS and MERS. The pathogen
17 outbreak was declared as a pandemic and by the time of this article, it has claimed 2.19
18 million lives. Computational biology research has provided a lot of insight into many of the
19 structural and functional proteins of the virus and the efforts continue.

20 *Methods:* We performed molecular docking of several SARS-CoV-2 proteins that are
21 responsible for its pathogenicity against N-acetyl-D-glucosamine via AutoDock Vina and
22 further analyzed the docked poses with molecular dynamics, we also performed a similar
23 experiment for both SARS-CoV-2 and anti-*Staphylococcus aureus* neutralizing antibodies to
24 establish the potential N-acetyl-D-glucosamine hold in inducing the immune system against
25 the virus.

26 *Results:* Our new molecular docking and molecular dynamic analysis results have confirmed
27 that SARS-CoV-2 spike receptor-binding domain (PDB: 6M0J), crystal structure of RNA-
28 binding domain of nucleocapsid phosphoprotein from SARS-CoV-2 monoclinic crystal form
29 (PDB: 6WKP), electron microscopy structure of refusion SARS-CoV-2 S ectodomain trimer
30 covalently stabilized in the closed conformation (PDB: 6X79), and X-ray diffraction structure
31 of SARS-CoV-2 main protease 3clpro at room temperature (damage-free XFEL monoclinic,
32 PDB: 7JVZ), and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine could bind on these proteins that play an important
33 role in SARS-CoV-2's infection. Moreover, our molecular docking analysis data support a

34 strong protein-ligand interaction of N-acetyl-D-glucosamine. These results were confirmed
35 with molecular dynamics studies and the conformational modeling could be used to predict
36 the possible protein-ligand interactions. Additionally, docking analysis against the D614G
37 mutant of the virus have shown that N-acetyl-D-glucosamine affinity was not affected by
38 mutations in the virus' receptor binding domain. Furthermore, our analysis on the affinity of
39 D-GlcNAc towards human antibodies has shown that it could potentially bind to both SARS-
40 CoV-2 proteins and antibodies hence further induce the immune system against the viral
41 infection.

42 *Conclusion:* Based on our predictive modelling work, N-acetyl-D-glucosamine holds the
43 potential to inhibit several SARS-CoV-2 proteins as well as induce an immune response
44 against the virus in host system.

45

46 *Keywords:* BioData mining, Drug repurposing; Molecular docking; Molecular dynamics; N-
47 acetyl-D-glucosamine; Protein modeling; SARS-CoV-2; Small-molecule inhibitors

48

49 **1. Introduction**

50

51 The SARS-CoV-2 outbreak started from a local seafood market in Huanan showed that
52 human-to-human transmission of the virus was not limited [1]. Coronaviruses have error-
53 prone RNA-dependent RNA polymerases, mutations, and recombination events occurring
54 frequently that raise the concern regarding its rapidly strengthening and its increased capacity
55 to cause disease [2]. Many mutations detected on the virus genome suggest the formation of
56 the strains with high pathogenicity and contagiousness, which makes the control of the
57 pathogen quite difficult. In a previous study, Baysal *et al.* (2021) have investigated unvarying
58 regions with less mutation than other parts of the genome on 134 different genome sequences
59 of the GISAID database from distinct parts of the world, using MAUVE. Afterwards, the
60 aligned sequences were converted to protein sequences using translate tool – ExPASyweb.
61 The amino acid sequence of the conserved region (ORF1ab region) was obtained [3], then
62 subjected to sequence for homology modeling and introduced N-acetyl-D-glucosamine (D-
63 GlcNAc) as a potential inhibitor for the protein model. As mentioned in our previous study,
64 D-GlcNAc has shown to have some antiviral properties that should be considered for SARS-
65 Cov-2 therapies [3]. Currently, there are some specific antiviral vaccines or therapies to treat
66 SARS-CoV-2, but their long-lasting effects remain unclear. Drug repurposing which is the

67 technique of searching for new benefits or purposes of the existing drugs will be beneficial for
 68 approving the drugs which may reduce the cost and time of drug development and lower the
 69 risk of unexpected side effects of the drug [4]. In this study, we analyzed the interaction of 4
 70 proteins related to the SARS-CoV-2 with D-GlcNAc using molecular docking and further
 71 validating the results with molecular dynamics [3]. The general workflow applied to each
 72 protein analyzed is shown in figure 1.

73

74

75 **Fig. 1.** General workflow applied for all the proteins analyzed in the study.

76 **2. Methods**

77

78 *2.1. Retrieving the protein structures*

79 We retrieved the crystal structure of SARS-CoV-2 spike receptor-binding domain
80 (PDB: 6M0J), crystal structure of RNA-binding domain of nucleocapsid phosphoprotein from
81 SARS-CoV-2 monoclinic crystal form (PDB: 6WKP), electron microscopy structure of
82 refusion SARS-CoV-2 S ectodomain trimer covalently stabilized in the closed conformation
83 (PDB: 6X79), and X-ray diffraction structure of SARS-CoV-2 main protease 3clpro at room
84 temperature (damage-free XFEL monoclinic, PDB: 7JVZ) from RCSB website. The structure
85 of the ligand D-GlcNAc was retrieved from PubChem (CID: 439174) [5-9].

86

87 *2.2. Preparation of structure files for molecular docking analysis*

88 As for structure preparations, all of the 4 protein PDB files had their water and
89 heteroatoms (except for ions) removed using UCSF Chimera, then they were loaded into
90 AutoDock 4.2 where only polar hydrogen atoms and Kollman charges were added, the
91 structures were then exported as PDBQT files. As for the ligand, it was prepared using a
92 similar procedure with further geometrical optimization using the MMFF94 forcefield [10-
93 12].

94

95 *2.3. Molecular docking analysis*

96 Docking experiments were performed using AutoDock Vina on a Linux cluster [13].
97 Docking of 6M0J and 6WKP were performed with exhaustiveness of 64 and 24 modes, the
98 grid box calculated for each were 25x50x20 Å from their center (-12.972, 19.833, 0.667) and
99 14x16x12 Å from their center (4.36, -5.444, 22.056) along their X, Y, and Z axes,
100 respectively. Blind docking experiments were performed for 6X79 and 7JVZ with
101 exhaustiveness of 128 and 32 modes, the grid box calculated for each were
102 122.456x130.663x149.16 Å and 40.222x63.997x61.273 Å from the center of the protein
103 along their X, Y, and Z axes, respectively. The best docking pose with the highest affinity
104 (lowest kcal/mol) was selected.

105

106 *2.4. Preparation of structure files for molecular dynamics analysis*

107 The best docking pose for each structure was produced using UCSF Chimera's
108 ViewDock plugin and later the protein and ligand (D-GlcNAc) were saved in separate files.

109 The ligands poses were submitted to LigParGen for the generation of topology and parameter
110 files using OPLS-AA forcefield [14-16]. The protein structure files for each protein were
111 generated using OPLS-AA/M topology for proteins in VMD using the psfgen builder plugin
112 [15,17]. The protein structure file (PSF) and the protein data bank file (PDB) for each protein
113 was merged with its corresponding ligand PSF and PDB files (from LigParGen) into a single
114 protein-ligand complex PSF and PDB files. Each protein-ligand complex was solvated with
115 water in a rectangular box, the box dimensions were determined such that every edge was 5 Å
116 away from the complex. The box was further neutralized with 0.15 mol/L NaCl such that a
117 distance of 5 Å was maintained between the ions and the solute and between the ions
118 themselves.

119

120 *2.5. Molecular dynamics analysis*

121 Molecular dynamics simulations were performed using the University of Illinois
122 Nanoscale Molecular Dynamics (NAMD) software [18]. Each simulation was run using the
123 solvated and ionized protein-ligand complex with OPLS-AA/M protein parameter files and
124 their respective D-GlcNAc parameter files from the LigParGen server, as for the water and
125 ions, the topology file from CHARMM-GUI was utilized [19]. All the protein-ligand
126 complexes were minimized (energy minimization) with the steepest descent algorithm under
127 NVT ensemble at 310 K for 50,000 steps except 6M0J which was minimized with NVT
128 ensemble at 310 K for 100,000 steps, the graphs of backbone Root-mean-square deviation
129 (RMSD) against the frames were plotted to check if the systems were successfully minimized.
130 After confirming the minimization, each protein-ligand complex was simulated for 1,000,000
131 steps (≈ 1 ns), each time step was set to 1 fs and the outputs were written to the trajectory
132 every 50 steps, the simulations were run under Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBC) with
133 space partitioning cutoff set to 10, initial and bath temperature set to 310 K with Langevin
134 dynamics at the same temperature. All the water molecules and the protein-ligand complex
135 were wrapped around the PBC. The graph of backbone RMSD against frames were plotted
136 for each simulation to analyze the protein-ligand complexes' stability.

137

138 *2.6. D-GlcNAc-Antibody affinity analysis*

139 Two neutralizing antibodies, one specific to the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein from PDB:
140 7JV2 and another anti-*Staphylococcus aureus* from PDB: 6P9H were extracted from their
141 structures via UCSF Chimera, the structures were prepared for docking with the same
142 configurations as done in the previous step, and blind docking was performed via AutoDock
143 Vina. The top pose for each antibody-D-GlcNAc was simulated via NAMD with the same
144 procedures and configurations as the previous molecular dynamic simulation. The backbone
145 RMSD of the antibodies and D-GlcNAc was plotted for further analysis.

146

147 3. Results

148

149 3.1. Molecular docking

150 Table 1 shows the results of the best-docked pose in the molecular docking experiment
151 using AutoDock Vina, all the results are promising as each one D-GlcNAc has shown a
152 decent affinity to each of the protein structure. The docking poses corresponding to the values
153 in table 1 are represented with hydrophobicity surface representation for 6M0J (a), 6WKP (b),
154 and 7JVZ (d) and with ribbon representation for 6X79 (c) using UCSF Chimera in figure 2
155 with red circles showing D-GlcNAc position. The log files showing all the poses generated by
156 AutoDock Vina are included in Supplementary data 1.

157

158 **Table 1.** Docking pose of D-GlcNAc with the highest affinity (lowest kcal/mol) to each of the
159 tested proteins from AutoDock Vina.

Docked structure	Affinity (kcal/mol)
6M0J	-5.1
6WKP	-6.6
6X79	-6.6
7JVZ	-5.6

160

161

162

163 **Fig. 2.** Best docking poses for tested protein. Hydrophobicity surface representation of the
 164 best docking pose with D-GlcNAc for a) 6M0J, b) 6WKP, d) 7JVZ and ribbon representation
 165 for of the best docking pose with D-GlcNAc for c) 6X79. Red circles showing where D-
 166 GlcNAc is positioned within the protein. Figures were produced with UCSF Chimera.

167

168 **Fig. 3.** Best docking poses for tested protein. Cartoon representation of the best docking pose
 169 of proteins (colored by secondary structures, clipped for visibility of the ligand) with D-
 170 GlcNAc for a) 6M0J, b) 6WKP, d) 7JVZ, and ribbon representation for the best docking pose
 171 with D-GlcNAc for c) 6X79. Figures were produced with PyMol [20].

172

173 The docked structures loaded into PyMol [20] had 5 Å away from the ligand. All the
 174 potential polar interactions within this range were highlighted with their distances measured
 175 (Fig. 3, 4).

176

177 **Fig. 4.** All potential polar interactions between D-GlcNAc (green stick) with a) 6M0J, b)
 178 6WKP, c) 6X79 and d) 7JVZ with 5 Å from D-GlcNAc as predicted by PyMol. The
 179 interactions between the residues as shown by yellow dots (length in Å). The amino acid
 180 residues are colored randomly for contrast.

181

182 3.2. Molecular dynamics

183 The RMSD for the backbone (C, Ca, and N) of each protein-ligand complex against
 184 their minimization plot was analyzed to check if the minimization steps have successfully

185 minimized the protein-ligand complex, as shown in figure 5, all the slopes are plateauing near
186 the end frames hence 100,000 steps for 6M0J and 50,000 steps for 6WKP, 6X79 and 7JVZ
187 have produced a minimized structure for the molecular dynamic simulation.
188

189
190 **Fig. 5.** Analysis of minimization trajectory. 100,000 step steepest descent minimization for
191 6M0J and 50,000 step steepest descent minimization for 6WKP, 6X79, and 7JVZ. Backbone
192 RMSD (Å) along the Y-axis and frames (50 fs distance between any 2 frames) along the X-
193 axis.

194
195 Similarly, the backbone RMSD of the protein in protein-ligand complex against their
196 corresponding frames were extracted and plotted, the RMSD of the ligand within the same
197 complex was also plotted in the same graph (Fig. 6). The data used for plotting the graphs of
198 both the minimization and production runs are included in Supplementary data 2.

199
 200 **Fig. 6.** Analysis of molecular dynamics trajectory. Backbone RMSD (Å) along the Y-axis and
 201 frames (50 fs distance between any 2 frames) along the X-axis for each protein-ligand
 202 complex 1,000,000 production runs. Redline indicating protein backbone RMSD and light
 203 blue indicating ligand RMSD.

204

205 3.3. Antibody-D-GLCNAC specificity analysis

206 Both the docking analysis of S2H13 neutralizing antibody Fab fragment and that of
 207 anti-*Staphylococcus aureus* antibody (STAU-281 Fab) with D-GlcNAc has shown an affinity
 208 of -6.5 kcal/mol and -6.2 kcal/mol which satisfies our hypothesis that D-GlcNAc has a
 209 significant affinity towards human antibodies (Fig. 7) regardless its specificity hence it has the
 210 potential to induce the immune response by bridging a bond between SARS-CoV-2 and
 211 antibodies. The RMSD analysis of both the antibodies tested has shown that D-GlcNAc
 212 remains at very close proximity to the antibodies (Fig. 7, 8), supporting our hypothesis
 213 further. The detailed logfile from the AutoDock Vina and the data used for the RMSD plot are
 214 included in Supplementary data 3 and 4, respectively.

215
 216 **Fig. 7.** Top docked poses of D-GlcNAc with (a) S2H13 neutralizing antibody Fab fragment
 217 from PDB 7JV2 and (b) STAU-281 Fab anti-*Staphylococcus aureus* antibody from PDB
 218 6P9H, images generated by PyMol, antibody structure represented as cartoons and colored by
 219 their secondary structure whereas D-GlcNAc is represented with sticks and colored by
 220 element (green).
 221

222
 223 **Fig. 8.** Analysis of molecular dynamics trajectory. Backbone RMSD (Å) along the Y-axis and
 224 frames (50 fs distance between any 2 frames) along the X-axis for each protein-ligand
 225 complex 1,000,000 production runs. Redline indicating protein backbone RMSD and light
 226 blue indicating ligand RMSD.

227
 228 **4. Discussion**

229
 230 The structural differences considering the active sites of both Mpro proteins cause
 231 difficulties in modelling for molecular target. In fact, a computational prediction studies
 232 carried out involves a massive virtual screening for Mpro inhibitors of SARS-CoV-2 using
 233 Deep Docking [21]. The recent studies focused on virtual screening for putative inhibitors of

234 the same main protease of SARS-CoV-2 relied on the clinically approved drugs [22-27] and
235 related to the compounds from different databases [28-30]. Nevertheless, they did not lead to
236 clinical success in the fight against SARS-CoV-2.

237 Molecular docking is a good tool to estimate the binding affinity between protein and
238 ligand by using scoring functions [31]. Molecular dynamics simulation as a computational
239 method provides insights into the interaction and atoms according to physics rules. [32].

240 It is also important to mention the UK, South African, and Brazilian variants of SARS-CoV-2
241 that have been circulating in the population (as of the time of this article). These variants are
242 shown to be present with higher transmissibility due to the collection of few mutations in its
243 spike protein sequence. The findings of Cheng et al. (2021) provide them a higher affinity to
244 the human ACE2 receptor, among the mutations, are the N501Y, K417N, and E484K
245 mutations [33]. All these mutations affect the receptor-binding domain of the spike protein
246 since D-GlcNAc as shown in figures 2 & 3 (c) interacts with the trans-membranal domain of
247 the spike protein. These mutations are irrelevant for the therapeutic potentials of D-GlcNAc
248 we had investigated, however, a molecular docking with the D614G variant of the virus
249 (PDB: 7KDK) and the results did not include any loss of affinity.

250 We assumed that the loading of D-GlcNAc binding on proteins playing role in
251 pathogenicity, the recognition of invasive SARS-CoV-2 individuals entering host cell through
252 ACE2 receptor side could be increased by the immunologic response. Additionally, D-
253 GlcNAc, which is present in the cell wall of bacteria, has been the reason for the recognition
254 of human IgG1 mAb (F598) through a large groove-shaped binding site cause of the entire
255 light- and heavy-chain interface embedded at least five GlcNAc residues receptor affinity,
256 makes it possible to recognize the bacterial cells [34].

257 It can be suggested that D-GlcNAc can shift immune response, which is responsible for
258 fighting with invaded bacteria [35], to SARS-CoV-2. In a previous study, N-acetyl-
259 glucosamine cluster antigens (TGCA) account for the highest immunoreactivity [36], which
260 could be suggested for the activation of the immune system against SARS-CoV-2. In another
261 study on HIV-1, the structures, along with glycan-array binding with the variation of the
262 oligosaccharide have shown to have an affinity that affects the neutralizing of antibodies
263 targeting the glycan-shielded trimer on the virus [37]. This D-GlcNAc stimulated mechanism
264 could also increase the defense capacity of the immunologic response to SARS-CoV-2
265 invasion. Furthermore, N-acetyl-D-glucosamine-coated polyamidoamine structures induced

266 upregulation of antibody formation on the rat recombinant cells [38] that the similar response
267 could be expected in human cell.

268

269 **5. Conclusion**

270

271 The SARS-CoV-2 epidemic has been a major reason threatening to human health and
272 resulted in an important economic recession in the world. As our previous findings indicated
273 that N-acetyl-D-glucosamine a potential drug suggesting strong interaction with proteins
274 involving the ORF1ab region. The data of the previous study showed a constantly unvarying
275 piece of sequence in whole paired genome sequences that can be used as a target origin for
276 designing an effective molecule to SARS-CoV-2. Our results could be used for drug
277 repurposing in the therapeutic options against SARS-CoV-2 by testing different
278 concentrations of D-GlcNAc to SARS-CoV-2.

279 In the presented study, we have also carried out molecular dynamics analysis on
280 different proteins of SARS-Cov-2 besides verification of our previous findings related to
281 binding possibilities with D-GlcNAc and docking analysis results. Our results confirmed and
282 highlighted the strong binding of D-GlcNAc to the domain region of proteins on aggressive
283 mutant variants (D614G). We believe that our findings will be beneficial for the
284 understanding of the new way for controlling the virus and its manipulative possibilities
285 considering the immune system of the body by mimicking and as occurred in the bacterial cell
286 recognition system.

287

288 **Acknowledgement**

289 The authors would like to thank Szek Lab from the Computer Engineering Department
290 of Mugla Sitki Kocman University for the Computational Resources they provided. The
291 authors also thank to anonymous reviewers for their insightful suggestions.

292

293 **Funding**

294 None.

295

296 **Author contribution**

297 Formulation of the idea: mr Baysal and Ragıp Soner Silme.

298 Analysis: Ömür Baysal and Naeem Abdul Ghafoor.

299 Writing: Ömür Baysal, Naeem Abdul Ghafoor and Ragıp Soner Silme.

300

301 **Declaration of competing interest**

302 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
303 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

304

305 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

306 Supplementary Data 1: AutoDock Vina log files for the viral protein docking

307 Supplementary Data 2: RMSD data sheet for viral protein molecular dynamics

308 Supplementary Data 3: AutoDock Vina log files for antibody docking

309 Supplementary Data 4: RMSD data sheet for antibody molecular dynamics

310

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